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PRAGMALINGUISTIC INTERPRETATION OF LITERARY DIALOGUE

Annotation

Pragmalinguistics is a new field of modern linguistics, which is a science that studies language factors in the field of human activity, paying attention to the psychological, social and cultural aspects of language activity in a general sense. Linguistic personality is a multifaceted, component and systematically organized set of linguistic competences, the interaction of the individual's spiritual world in the totality of specific social, ethnic, psychological, aesthetic features. From a pragmatic point of view, the linguistic personality is analyzed through the following factors: age, social status, profession, nationality and role relations.

Key words: Pragmalinguistics, linguistics, linguistic personality, age, social status, profession, nationality, pragmatic factor.

ПРАГМАЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКАЯ ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИЯ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ДИАЛОГА

Аннотация

Прагмалингвистика – это новая область современного языкознания, представляющая собой науку, изучающую языковые факторы в сфере деятельности человека, уделяя внимание психологическим, социальным и культурным аспектам языковой деятельности в общем смысле. Языковая личность представляет собой многогранную, составную и системно организованную совокупность языковых компетенций, взаимодействие духовного мира личности в совокупности конкретных социальных, этнических, психологических, эстетических особенностей. С прагматической точки зрения языковая личность анализируется через следующие факторы: возраст, социальный статус, профессию, национальность и ролевые отношения.

Ключевые слова: Прагмалингвистика, языкознание, языковая личность, возраст, социальный статус, профессия, национальность, прагматический фактор.

BADIIY DIALOGNING PRAGMALINGVISTIK TALQINI

Annotatsiya

Pragmalingvistika zamonaviy tilshunoslikning yangi bir sohasi bo'lib, u umumiy ma'noda til faoliyatining psixologik, ijtimoiy va madaniy jihatlari e'tibor qaratib, inson faoliyati sohasidagi til omillarini o'rganadigan fandır. Lingvistik shaxs - bu ko'p qirrali, komponentli va tizimli ravishda tashkil etilgan lingvistik kompetentsiyalar to'plami, shaxsning ma'naviy olamining o'ziga xos ijtimoiy, etnik, psixologik, estetik xususiyatlari yaxlitligidagi o'zaro munosabati. Pragmatik nuqtai nazardan lingvistik shaxs quyidagi omillar ya'ni, yosh, ijtimoiy mavqei, kasb, millat va rol munosabatlar orqali tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Pragmalingvistika, tilshunoslik, lingvistik shaxs, yosh, ijtimoiy mavqei, kasb, millat, pragmatik faktor.

Kirish. XX asrning 70-yillari boshlarida tilshunoslikka bo'lgan qiziqish o'zgardi. Tilshunoslar o'z ye'tiborlarini tilga bo'lgan tizimli yozdashuvdan vaziyatdagi va harakatdagi til yondashuviga o'zgartirishdi. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, tilga munosabat uni rasmiy birlik deb yemas, balki aloqa birligi sifatida qabul qilishga o'tkazildi. Yuqorida aytib o'tilgan o'zgarish natijasida tilshunoslikning sotsiolingvistika, psixolingvistika, kommunikativ lingvistika, matn lingvistikasi, pragmalingvistika kabi yangi sohaları paydo bo'ldi.

Pragmalingvistika lingvistikaning yangi sohasi bo'lib, bir qancha tilshunoslar va tadqiqotchilar unga turlicha ta'rif berishgan. Ko'plab olimlar tomonidan taqdim etilgan turli xil talqinlar mavjud. Turli xil taxminlar pragmalingvistikani har xil tomondan belgilaydi. Morris, Van Diyk, Arutyunova, Stepanov, Ashurova, Galieva va boshqalar pragmalingvistika fanini turlicha talqin qilishgan.

Mavzuga oid adabiyotlar tahlili. Matn kommunikativ munosabat vositasi yekan, pragmatika matnning asosiy parametrlaridan biridir. Turli xil olimlar pragmatikaga oid turli xil taxminlarni taqdim yetadilar. Tilshunoslikning Ensiklopedik lug'atida keltirilgan ta'rifga ko'ra, pragmatika (yunoncha pragma, pragmatos-harakat) nutqda til belgilarining turli funksiyalarini o'rganadigan semiotika va lingvistikaning tadqiqot sohasi. "Pragmatika" atamasi birinchi bo'lib Ch. U. Morris tomonidan XX asrning 30-yillarida semiotikaning uchta tarmog'idan biri sifatida ishlatilgan. U pragmatikani

belgilarning o'z foydalanuvchilariga bo'lgan munosabati deb ta'riflagan[1].

Pragmalingvistikani "tilni kontekstda o'rganish" deb ta'riflagan T. van Deykning fikriga ko'ra, pragmatikalar lingvistik nazariyaning ajralmas tarkibiy qismi bo'lib, maqomi sintaksis va semantikaga taqqoslanadi[2].

Pragmalingvistika mustaqil tadqiqot sohasiga sifatida pragmatikadan ajratilgach, N.D. Arutyunova tomonidan unga "nutqda lingvistik belgilarning ishlashi o'rganiladigan semiotik va lingvistik tadqiqotlar sohasi" deb ta'rif berilgan yedi va uning doirasida o'rganilgan masalalar nutq mavzusi, so'zlovchilar, ularning o'zaro munosabati va muloqot holatidan iborat[3].

Pragmalingvistika muammolarini muhokama qilgan V. Karasik uni tushuntirishda uchta yo'malishga tayanishni ajratib ko'rsatdi: a) muloqotga oid (nutq aktlari to'g'risida) b) funktsional (ritorik, uslubiy) va psixolingvistik (nutq yaratish va idrok yetish)[4].

Shuningdek, pragmalingvistika Yu.S. Stepanov fikricha og'zaki muloqotning o'ziga xos sharoitlarida tinglovchiga yoki o'quvchiga yeng muvaffaqiyatli ta'sir qilish, ko'zlangan maqsadga samarali yerishish uchun tilda mavjud bo'lgan yeng maqbul vositalarni tanlash bilan shug'ullanadigan fan sifatida tavsiflanadi [5].

D.U. Ashurova pragmalingvistikaga quyidagicha ta'riflaydi: "Pragmalingvistika – bu kommunikativ lingvistikaning

yo'nalishlaridan biri bo'lib, uni umumiy ma'noda til faoliyatining psixologik, ijtimoiy va madaniy jihatlariga yetibor qarab, inson faoliyati sohasidagi til omillarini o'rganadigan fan deb ta'riflash mumkin" [6].

Barcha fikrlarni umumlashtirib, pragmatik talqin qilishda quyidagi jihatlar va yondashuvlarni ta'kidlashimiz mumkin:

- belgi va uning foydalanuvchilari o'rtasidagi munosabatlar (Morris, 1978);
- kontekstli shartlilik, tildan foydalanish, kontekstdagi til (Susov, 1985) [8];
- nutqning manzilga ta'siri, muvaffaqiyatli va samarali muloqotga ta'sir yetuvchi omillar (Kisileva, 1978) [9];
- nutq aloqalarining talqin etuvchi jihatlar (Arutyunova, 1989);
- til maqsadli kommunikativ faoliyat vositasi sifatida (Grays, 1985) [10];
- o'zaro tushunish va tildan foydalanishning maqsadga muvofiqligi muammosi (van Deyk, 1977).

Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, ushbu jihatlarining barchasi ham bir-biriga muvofiq yemas, lekin ular o'zaro bir-birini to'ldiradi.

- **Tadqiqot metodologiyasi.** Pragmatik talqin tushunchasi bu lingvistik shaxs tushunchasidir. Tilshunoslikda lingvistik shaxs nazariyasi Yu.N. Karaulov tomonidan to'liq ishlab chiqilgan. Karaulovning kontseptsiyasi va ushbu sohadagi boshqa tadqiqotlarga tayanib, quyidagi ta'rifni berish mumkin: lingvistik shaxs - bu ko'p qirrali, komponentli va tizimli ravishda tashkil yetilgan lingvistik kompetensiyalar to'plami, shaxsning ma'naviy olamining o'ziga xos ijtimoiy, etnik, psixologik, estetik xususiyatlari yaxlitligidagi o'zaro munosabati [7].

Tahlil va natijalar. Lingvistik shaxs modeli nutq qatlamida aks ettirilgan semantik, pragmatik, kognitiv, madaniy qatlamlarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Quyidagi J.D.Salingerning "Javdarzordagi xaloskor" (The Catcher in the Rye) asaridagi dialog orqali yosh va rol munosabatlarini tahlil qilamiz:

"I brush my teeth. Don't gimme that."

"No, you don't. I've seen you, and you don't," I said. I didn't say it nasty, though. I felt sort of sorry for him, in a way. I mean it isn't too nice, naturally, if somebody tells you you don't brush your teeth. "Stradlater's all right He's not too bad," I said. "You don't know him, that's the trouble."

"I still say he's a sonuvabitch. He's a conceited sonuvabitch."

"Stop calling me 'Ackley kid,' God damn it. I'm old enough to be your lousy father."

"No, you're not." Boy, he could really be aggravating sometimes. He never missed a chance to let you know you were sixteen and he was eighteen. "In the first place, I wouldn't let you in my goddam family," I said.

"Well, just cut out calling me-" (J. D. Salinger, "The Catcher in the Rye")

Ushbu Xolden va uning do'sti o'rtasidagi dialog norasmiy va so'zlashuv uslubiga xos so'z va birikmalariga (gimme, kid, damn, lousy, goddam) va qo'pol so'zlarga (sonuvabitch) to'la, bu esa lingvistik shaxslarning yosh va rol munosabatlari kabi pragmatik faktorlarni ifoda etadi.

Keyingi dialog esa lingvistik shaxsning boshqa bir tomonini, ya'ni ikki muloqotchilar ham bir hil kasbga ega ekanligini ko'rsatadi:

'You will excuse me, Chunk,' said Ikey. 'I must make a prescription that is to be called for soon.'

'Say,' said McGowan, looking up suddenly, 'say, Ikey, ain't the read rug of some kind-some kind of powders that'll make a girl like you better if you give'e mother?'

Ikey's lip beneath his nose curled with the scorn of superior enlightenment; but before he could answer, McGowan continued:

'Tim Lacy told me once that he got some from a croaker up town and fed'e m to his girl in soda water. From the very first dose he was ace-high and everybody else looked like thirty cents to her. They was married in less than two weeks.' (O'Henry, "The Love-philtre of Ikey Schoenste")

Bu namunada lingvistik shaxslarning kasbi kabi pragmatik ma'lumot kursoratlangan. Ushbu hikoyaning qahramonlari Ikey va MakGovan ikkalasi ham farmatsevtlar. Ularning nutqi tibbiy sohaga oid so'zlarga boy (prescription, powder, soda water, first dose). Bundan tashqari, ushbu dialogdagi jargon va so'zlashuv uslubiga oid so'zlar (ain't, give'e, fed'e) so'zlashuvchilar bir-birlariga o'zaro yaqin ekanini ko'rsatadi. Bundan shu ko'rinadiki, ikki muloqotchilar ham o'zaro tanish va bir xil kasb vakili.

Lingvopragmatik tahlil rol munosabati omilini qabul qilganligi sababli, o'qituvchi va talaba o'rtasidagi suhbat talabaning xonadoshi bilan suhbatidan farq qiladi. Keling, ikkalasini solishtiraylik:

It started, all right. "What's the matter with you, boy?" old Spencer said. He said it pretty tough, too, for him. "How many subjects did you carry this term?"

"Five, sir."

"Five. And how many are you failing in?" "Four.".....

He started handling my exam paper like it was a turd or something. "We studied the Egyptians from November 4th to December 2nd," he said. "You chose to write about them for the optional essay question. Would you care to hear what you had to say?"

"No, sir, not very much," I said (J. D. Salinger, "The Catcher in the Rye")

Muloqotda ko'rib turganimizdek, janob Spenser o'qituvchi rovida, nazoratchi, tanqidchi. U ishlatadigan so'zlar (How many subjects did you carry this term, And how many are you failing in, We studied the Egyptians from November 4th to December 2nd) uning o'qituvchi ekanligiga ishora qiladi, u o'z shogirdini nazorat qiladi va tekshiradi. O'z navbatida, o'quvchi juda qo'rqqoq, u qisqa javoblar beradi (Five, Four, No, not very much), qaram, itoatkor va hurmatli (Sir). Biroq, Xolden guruhdoshi Akli bilan muloqot qilganda o'zini ancha erkin his qiladi. Ularning nutqi norasmiy va so'zlashuv uslubiga oid so'zlarga (sonuvabitch, goddam), jargonlarga (crumpy) to'la bo'lib, ularning yoshi va rol munosabatlarini, ular orasida masofa yo'qligini bildiradi:

"He's got this superior attitude all the time," Ackley said. "I just can't stand the sonuvabitch. You'd think he--"

"Do you mind cutting your nails over the table, hey?" I said. "I've asked you about fifty--"

"He's got this goddam superior attitude all the time," Ackley said. "I don't even think the sonuvabitch is intelligent. He thinks he is. He thinks he's about the most--"

"Ackley! For Chrissake. Willya please cut your crumby nails over the table? I've asked you fifty times." (J. D. Salinger, "The Catcher in the Rye")

Yuqoridagi dialoglardan kelib chiqqan holda shuni aytish kerakki, biz yosh, kasb va rol munosabatlari kabi pragmatik omillarni tahlil qildik.

Xulosa va takliflar. Xulosa qilib shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, pragmatik talqin juda ko'p qirrali fandır. Shuning uchun pragmatik talqin sohasiga tegishli ko'plab tushunchalar mavjud. Lingvopragmatikani har xil tomondan talqin qilish mumkin. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, pragmatik talqin - bu til omillarini insonning psixologik, ijtimoiy va madaniy jihatlariga mos ravishda o'rganadigan fandır. Xulosa qilib shuni ta'kidlash kerakki:

a) adabiy muloqot til shaxsini ochishning asosiy vositalaridan biridir

b) pragmatik nuqtai nazardan esa uning quyidagi omillarini hisobga olish kerak: yoshi, ijtimoiy mavqei, kasbi, millati va rol munosabatlari.

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